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A selection-based strategy identifies a minimal set of surface antigens that mark tumor cells for immune clearance and immune receptors that support tumor surveillance.

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The receptors identified included Fcgbp, Siglec12, Cd74 and KIR3DL2, with critical tumor antigens including CTAGE5, PNMA5 and Sdccag1. The mechanisms described by the gene products identified following *in vivo* selection included one controlled by presence or absence of HLA-DPB2.